

CRITERIA OF THE CLUSTER SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the creation of competitive goods based on the organization of innovative production - the integration of enterprises of the same industry located in the city, district and region, and educational, scientific, engineering, consulting, standardization, certification and other services in a single technological chain.

"Cotton-textile cluster" is a large-scale project, one of the conditions for the development of the economy. Familiarity with it, a deeper understanding of its essence is important not only for industry professionals, experts, economists, but also for the general public. After all, the fate of all of us depends on this land. Development requires innovation. The more we learn about them, the more we contribute to development.

A small level of integration is the formation of a new system for managing the country's economy, the creation of "clusters", which include enterprises and organizations that produce the final product and are geographically close to each other.

The purpose of clusters is to focus on the creation of competitive goods based on the organization of innovative production - the integration of enterprises of the same industry located in the city, district and region, and educational, scientific,

engineering, consulting, standardization, certification and other services in a single technological chain. At the same time, such an important aspect as employment is manifested.

Globalization and the deepening of integration processes in the global economy require a comprehensive study of both the internal strengths and weaknesses of agribusiness, as well as its external opportunities and risks in the market. One of such opportunities is to organize an agro-industrial group based on a cluster model.

The cluster model is widely used in world practice as a tool to increase the competitiveness of an economic group, region, and country as a whole. The main features of the cluster model are: the ability of the group to increase its share in foreign markets; the availability of favorable conditions (raw materials, qualified personnel, infrastructure, training centers,

scientific institutions, etc.) on the territory; the breadth of opportunities for effective participation of participants in the group in exchange for the active use of the group by the state, etc.

Materials and methods.

After the 1980s, we can observe the achievements of 3 important scientific schools (American, British, Scandinavian and others) in the development of cluster theory.

The compatibility of added value and cluster chain, regional learning concepts are also included in this group.

From the evolution of cluster theory, two main descriptions of it can be distinguished.

Firstly, the activities of enterprises and firms integrated into the cluster should be clearly linked to the market of the same type of goods. Such a connection can be vertical (a chain of purchases and sales) and horizontal (additional departments and services, related specific costs, the use of technologies or institutions, and other connections).

Secondly, clusters are a group of geographically close interconnected enterprises that develop competitiveness as a result of stabilization of economic and social relations between them, creating opportunities for creating more added value and sales in the market.

Industrial clusters are primarily able to withstand competition within this network in local and global markets.

Therefore, in the conditions of innovative economic development, especially in the current period, when traditional methods of economic development do not provide sufficient advantages, the use of cluster theory is the most optimal way.

Clustering can also be considered as a new economic system that fully meets the requirements of national and regional development in order to increase the competitiveness of enterprises by accelerating their innovation activities and to resist the strong influence of global competition.

The role of the state in the formation of clusters plays an important role.

In developed countries, there is experience in using clusters in the formation and management of an innovative economy.

Experience of foreign countries

High-tech agro-industrial clusters are common in all US states. Large agro-clusters are located in Washington, Oklahoma, Louisiana, and wine production is in California. High-performance clusters can be seen in the "Information Technology" clusters of Silicon Valley and the "Kinification" of Hollywood. In Europe (Germany, France, Italy, Bulgaria, Greece, the Netherlands, England, Switzerland, Denmark and other countries), high-tech agricultural clusters are widespread.

In France, in 1986, the Agropolis Association was established in Montpellier to coordinate the activities of agricultural enterprises, educational and research institutions in order to enter the European and world markets for technology and innovation.

Since 2001, the Stockbridge Technology Center, an innovative agro-industrial cluster in the UK, has been conducting research and training programs in the field of home agriculture, horticulture and vegetable growing. The center has modern greenhouses and high-tech laboratories on 70 hectares of irrigated land, ranging from 12 to 1000 square meters, which are controlled by 40 computers.

Austria also focuses on the specialization of clusters, the promotion of interaction between agro-industrial and research enterprises, the reduction of barriers to the management of innovation programs and the formation of competition centers.

In Danish agriculture, animal husbandry is more important than agriculture, agricultural products are used more for feed, the role of dairy products in animal husbandry is higher than in the meat sector, therefore dairy clusters (for example, the well-known cluster "Dairy Vertical") are widespread.

Over the past 30 years, the Government of Chile has taken bold steps to increase its share in the global market by integrating into the wine industry and expanding the ranks of large companies equipped with modern technologies. A wine cluster was created for this purpose. It includes interconnected associations within the network, educational institutions, government agencies and agencies, research centers, network media, postmen and subcontractors.

Famous European mayors have returned to the country with their investments, new technologies, product sales and export opportunities. As a result, Chile is the fifth largest exporter of wine on the world market.

In Russia, too, more than 200 projects on the formation and development of clusters are being implemented in all sectors of the economy, including in the agro-industrial complex.

The Concept of Development of Territorial-industrial clusters, adopted by the Ministry of Economic Development in 2008, consists of three blocks: promoting the institutional development of clusters; increasing the competitiveness of cluster participants;

creating favorable conditions for cluster development.

Currently, in the Biocomplex cluster of the Tomsk region (new soft and sharp wheat varieties resistant to fungal and fungal diseases have been created, then it is planned to create an AgroPARK, including deep grain processing, biotechnology, petrochemical production), the Baltika cluster in the Tula region (17 varieties of oats suitable for brewing have been grown at 672 experimental sites of the research station (included in the register of achievements of Russia),

In the Kemerovo region agro-industrial brand "KalinaMalina" (7 stores and 40 farmers), in the Vologda region cluster "Biotechnology" (with JSC "PhosAgro"), etc. the process of creating such modern agro-clusters in the regions has significantly accelerated.

Clusters are well developed in the UK, Holland, Germany, USA, Denmark, France, Italy, Finland, India. Clusters prevail in Denmark, Finland and Sweden.

Cluster structures successfully operate in the light industry of Switzerland, Austria, Italy, Denmark, India, Korea, Pakistan, China and Turkey, the chemical and mechanical industries in Germany, as well as in the food and cosmetics industry in France.

The process of cluster formation is becoming more active in Southeast Asia, China, Singapore, Japan and other countries.

In Germany, for example, until recently, the development of regional clusters took place without state intervention. However, in 2003, the Government drew attention to cluster initiatives. This was done primarily in the design of high-tech industries. The state intends to combine the efforts of

industrial and scientific centers not only at the expense of local, but also other sources.

Thus, in the analysis of foreign and domestic researchers, the concept of "cluster" is defined as follows:

- cluster - a group of enterprises united in a single industry and interconnected.
- cluster - a group of enterprises located in the same geographical area and forming a single network.
- cluster - a group of interconnected and complementary companies, institutions operating in a single geographical area in certain territories.
- cluster - a group of enterprises that are functionally connected horizontally and vertically.
- cluster - a group of interconnected and complementary enterprises, research institutes in the form of collective, private and semi-collective.
- Cluster - a group of commercial and non-profit organizations that serves to ensure the competitiveness of each enterprise included in the group.
- Cluster - a production complex based on regional concentration and uniting suppliers of goods and raw materials, large producers connected in a technological chain.

As the President of the country Sh.M.Mirziyoyev noted, it is advisable to create a cluster system in all directions.

Indeed, the creation of cluster systems in the oil and gas, chemical, biotechnological, pharmaceutical, computer, automotive, transport, food, educational, fish, poultry, beekeeping, silk and other industries will increase funding for research and development, improve quality, research increases the level of technical support for their work, create new opportunities for participation in investment projects

abroad, training and advanced training of scientific and pedagogical personnel.

In addition, in the cluster system, educational and research centers will have ample opportunities and conditions for the creation of new scientific and methodological developments, their short-term testing, greater stimulation of production and scientific personnel and specialists, the invention of new products under the Uzbek brand.

Results.

Also, research centers for training international cluster coordinators and Cluster Project Councils will appear in our country.

One of the most reasonable ways is to form clusters in the textile and light industry system of Uzbekistan not on the basis of the country, but on the basis of specific economic and social conditions in the regions, based on the essence of the theory of clusters.

The cotton-textile cluster covers not only light industry, but also dozens of sectors on its way, such as agriculture, food industry, pharmaceuticals, construction goods.

The need to find effective ways of producing raw cotton is also explained by the fact that in the conditions of Uzbekistan, the possibilities of land productivity have not been fully used.

This is confirmed by a comparison of some indicators of agriculture in Uzbekistan and developed countries. For example, the Netherlands, with a population of 16 million people and 1.038 million hectares of arable land (60% of which are developed by the sea), produced agricultural products worth \$ 131 billion, while Uzbekistan, with a population of 32 million and 4.4 million hectares, is only \$ 13.2 billion.

The main consumer of raw cotton in Uzbekistan is the textile industry, which plays an important role in the industrial complex of the republic. Undoubtedly, the development of the textile industry is also directly related to the state of the cotton industry.

World experience shows that in the textile industry, a vertically integrated system can be efficient and competitive, from the cultivation and initial processing of raw cotton to its subsequent processing and production of finished products in cotton factories (for example, yarn, knitwear, fabrics and clothing). before the conversion.

It is impossible to create a competitive product with high added value without introducing new, modern approaches to the economy.

In this regard, we can give an example of step-by-step actions taken in our country on the initiative of the distinguished President.

In order to accelerate the development of the textile and knitwear industry, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 15, 2017 "On measures to create a modern cotton and textile cluster in the Syrdarya region" PP-3279 made the first first step. According to this decision, 18 thousand hectares of land in Mirzaabad district and 5 thousand hectares in Khavas district were transferred to the joint venture "Century Cluster" LLC.

The Company carries out mutual settlements in accordance with the principles of fair remuneration and social application of work performed on the basis of employment contracts with farms in these areas, and analyzes finished products with higher added value in foreign

markets. Export at set prices based on marketing.

Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2016 No. PP-2687 "On the Program of measures for the development of the textile and clothing industry for 2017-2021".

Also, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017 No. PF-5285 "On measures to accelerate the development of the textile and knitwear industry", a wide range of high-quality textile and knitwear is produced in the country. Comprehensive measures are being taken to increase the export potential of local producers. Over the past period, the necessary legal framework and favorable conditions for the development of the textile and clothing industry have been formed.

The State Committee for Privatization and Competition Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with Uzpakhtasanoat JSC and the Uztextile Industrial Association, registered 16 cotton gins and 68 cotton gins located on the territory of the cotton and textile industries and clusters, and assessed their condition. Important directions of further reform of the textile industry have been identified. A roadmap for the accelerated development of the textile and clothing industry of Uzbekistan based on clustering has been approved. The creation of the first pilot production cluster by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was aimed at:

- further deepening of structural changes and reduction of state participation in agriculture;
- attracting foreign investments to create an integrated cluster system of innovative

development of the agro-industrial complex;

- Introduction of effective methods of growing raw cotton and organization of deep processing of agricultural raw materials;

- Improving the efficiency of production and wages in agriculture.

The ultimate goal of this pilot industrial cluster was the production of competitive regional products with high added value and on this basis the solution of many problems in the regions, namely: efficient use of labor and material resources, budget replenishment, export opportunities, social issues.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5285 dated December 14, 2017 "On measures to accelerate the development of the textile and knitwear industry"
2. By the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 15, 2017 "On measures to create a modern cotton and textile cluster in the Syrdarya region" PP-3279
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2016 No. PP-2687 "On the Program of measures for the development of the textile and clothing industry for 2017-2021".
4. 4.Послание Президента Республики Узбекистан Ш.Мирзиёева в Олий Мажлис. 28 декабря 2019 года. Народное слово.
5. 5Халматжанова Г.Д. Локомотив аграрного сектора экономики. Ж .: Образование и наука в России и за рубежом. : Москва. №3, 2020.
6. 6.Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Райимджанова, Г. Х. (2020). Кластерный механизм-способ модернизации текстильной отрасли Узбекистана. Межвузовский научный конгресс:" Высшая школа: научные исследования". *НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ*, 28.
7. 7.Khalmatjanova, G. D. (2020). Mechanisms of formation of agricultural clusters in the economy of Uzbekistan. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 10(12), 847-852.
8. 8.Халматжанова, Г. Д. (2021). НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО КЛАСТЕРА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Scientific progress*, 2(3), 179-186.
9. 9.Халматжанова, Г. (2020). КЛАСТЕРЫ-ФАКТОР, ОПРЕДЕЛЯЮЩИЙ РАЗВИТИЕ АГРАРНОГО СЕКТОРА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. *Редакционная коллегия: ПМ Першукевич, академик РАН*, 319.
10. Halmathanova, G. J. (2020). The locomotive of the agricultural sectorz. *Образование и наука в России и за рубежом*, (3), 55-56.
11. Халматжанова, Г. Д. (2019). Модернизация и диверсификация-приоритетная задача сельского хозяйства Республики Узбекистан. *Образование и наука в России и за рубежом*, (16), 373-377.
12. Рахимов, Д. (2021). DETERMINED CRITERIA FOR DIVERSIFICATION IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
13. Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Райимджанова, Г. Х. (2020). Переработка сельхозпродукции и дальнейшее развитие пищевой промышленности Республики Узбекистан. In *НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИИ-СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ КОНЦЕПЦИИ* (pp. 38-43).

14. Халматжанова, Г. Д. (2020). ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ. In МИНТАҚА ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАШНИНГ МОЛИЯВИЙ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ЖИҲАТЛАРИ (pp. 26-34).
15. Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Мирзаахмадова, З. М. (2021). " ХЛОПКОВО-ТЕКСТИЛЬНЫЙ КЛАСТЕР"-ПРИОРИТЕТНОЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ РАЗВИТИЯ НАШЕЙ СТРАНЫ. Евразийский Союз Ученых, (3-3 (84)), 20-21.
16. Рахимов, Д. (2019). Свободно-экономические зоны-расширение экспортного потенциала Узбекистана. Архивариус, (12 (45)), 42-44.
17. Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Бахрамов, А. Х. (2020). ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ УСТОЙЧИВОГО И СБАЛАНСИРОВАННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕГИОНОВ. In МИНТАҚА ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАШНИНГ МОЛИЯВИЙ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ЖИҲАТЛАРИ (pp. 219-225).
18. Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Маннопова, М. С. (2020). РАЗВИТИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ С УЧЁТОМ ТЕНДЕНЦИЙ РАЗВИТИЯ МИРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ. In МИНТАҚА ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАШНИНГ МОЛИЯВИЙ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН ЖИҲАТЛАРИ (pp. 238-244).
19. Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Мадаминов, Ж. (2008). ИНВЕСТИЦИИ-СТИМУЛЯТОР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РОСТА. Вопросы экономических наук, (4), 80-81.
20. Халматжанова, Г. Д. (2021). РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕКСТИЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН.
21. Халматжанова, Г. Д., & Мадаминов, Ж. (2008). Конкурентоспособность-повышение качества продукции. Проблемы экономики, (3), 33-34.